

IMPACT OF MOBILE PHONES IN LEARNING

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Mobile phones accelerate learning, helps teachers and students communicate remotely. That is, through phones, young people can find teachers from one corner of the world and get the knowledge and skills they want from them. This article survey both the positive and negative impacts of mobile phones in education, highlighting their role in modern learning environments and suggesting strategies for effective and balanced use.

Key words: Mobile apps, applications, smartphones, education, educational platforms.

Introduction

Now we are living in the age of technology. There are many devices that help make our lives easier. Globally, "People around the world have adopted this new and exciting technology as one of the most important required facility in their everyday life" [Fawareh & Jusoh, 2017]. Globally, the explosion of smartphones and its related devices has greatly transformed teaching and learning in developed nations where developing nations are not the exception [Tagoe, 2014]. In 1876 The Scottish inventor A.G. Bell invented the first electroacoustic device the-- telephone has many benefits and, unfortunately, drawback aspects for a person, including people's education. Phones and similar devices can help you learn something new or reinforce your knowledge .If I give an example from myself, I learned English at home by phone. That is, by using a lot of dictionaries and participating in online classes.

Regrettably, many bad situations are observed among children and students nowadays due to excessive use of phones. The worst is that: too much connection to the phone and the Internet can weaken the ability of young people to communicate face-to-face. As a result, they pay less attention to social interactions in real life and feel uncomfortable in a group. [Kuznekoff, J.H 2015,]says that: Mobile phones in class can help and hurt students learning. Social networks, games and other applications can reduce attention to the lesson. Cases of academic dishonesty (copying, searching for answer on the internet) may increase during telephone examinations. On the other hand, some researchers have posited that mobile phones could contribute positively to student learning when used productively in the classroom [Ledbetter & Finn, 2013]; [O'Bannon & Thomas, 2015]. Being constantly in front of the screen can cause eye strain, insomnia and neck pain .Inactivity may increase due to the phone.

Therefore, develop the habit of exercising or going for a walk every day. Make a plan to reduce the amount of time you spend on your phone each day. For example, try not to spend more than 2-3 hours in front of the screen. I believe that only then you can protect your health. Furthermore, the cost of permanent internet and new devices can be economically prohibitive. Including that there are a lot of useful sides. Through the internet students can find any information get acquainted with electronic textbooks, articles and scientific materials.

The use of smartphones in learning has become the latest trend in higher education where an individual may not necessarily need a computer set to access electronic learning materials. The phenomenal roles of the smartphone in learning have been revealed by numerous authors such as in the works of Walk, [Rashid, & Elder 2010], that, smartphones have made learning more flexible. Online courses, mobile apps, and e-books make it possible to study anywhere, anytime. Students and teachers can communicate quickly through social networks, messengers and special educational platforms. For example, teachers can send class schedules, homework assignments, or important announcements to students and discuss topics covered. At the same time, students can ask questions to teachers online and get quick answers. Also it's possible to write notes from lessons through smartphones and save them in audio or video form. Through mobile applications, students can study independently at their own convenience. Applications such as Duolingo, Memrise, Anki make language learning interactive and interesting. This is especially useful for distance learning and self-development. Each student can choose the apps and tools that suit their learning style. If young people attend

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classes in this way, they will not suffer from financial problems, because it may not be possible for everyone to attend classes every day.

Through Google, Wikipedia and other knowledge platforms, students can quickly find the necessary information. Of course, they can also save time through this. Because quickly finding the information you are looking for is useful in every way. Not all information on the Internet is reliable, which can lead to incorrect knowledge. Therefore, it is necessary to be careful.

Conclusion

We can conclude that the use of telephone and other gadgets in education is very important nowadays. They make teaching and learning easy and convenient. Also, online resources increase the effectiveness of education. However, excessive phone use can be distracting, detrimental to health, and can lead to permanent addiction. In addition, face-to-face communication with loved ones is also the cause of loss. Therefore, it is necessary to use them purposefully and in moderation

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